

Modern conditions for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers through distance learning

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Annotation: This article describes the content of the formation of professional and methodological competence of future primary school teachers, the conditions and criteria for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers through distance learning.

Keywords: professional competence, methodological competence, knowledge, skills, qualifications, theoretical knowledge, organizational-motivational, process, integrative, cognitive.

The development of education in the world and the transition from education based on the complex sustainable development of mankind to the paradigm of active-competent education has led to an increase in demand for competitive personnel in line with modern trends in society. In the context of globalization, the quality of higher education ensures the country's sustainable competitiveness and "improves the process and tools for assessing the quality of education, introduces mechanisms to determine the results achieved". [5, p. 48]. In order to improve the methodological training of classroom teachers, the issue of "organizing an effective learning process in primary education" has become especially relevant.

Organization and updating of the content of higher education in the world on the basis of modern requirements, integration with science and industry, methodological and methodological support of preparation of future teachers for quasi-professional activities, information and communication education in e-learning environment per minute, extensive research has been conducted in the field of distance learning

opportunities. At the same time, it is important to improve the professional and methodological training of future teachers who are able to work at the level of world standards in their field, competitive in the labor market, socially and professionally active, based on a qualified approach to modern education.

At a time when the requirements for the methodological training of future primary school teachers are constantly changing in modern conditions, the study of best international practices, the development of didactic bases, pedagogical conditions, content and structure, criteria and it is important to develop theoretical and practical bases for improving the level of formation, methods, tools, model, quality of teaching, as well as the methodological training of future primary school teachers in a pedagogical higher education institution on the basis of a competency approach.

To achieve this, it is necessary to develop students' professional skills and competencies by teaching them to apply the knowledge acquired in various fields in everyday life in the stages of continuing education. In today's era of globalization, one of the main tasks of education is not only to educate students and build skills and competencies based on their knowledge, but also to develop the ability to apply them in practice. This set the task of introducing a competent approach to teaching all subjects.

According to the definition of the concept of qualification in the "Encyclopedia of Pedagogy", qualification (Arabic: ability, talent; quality, habit) - experience, skills, abilities acquired as a result of mastering the profession, work; an automated skill that results from a student's in-depth mastery of a particular learning material and profession.

Knowledge - set of scientific, practical information, concepts about an objective being or specific areas (scientific, cultural, educational, military, etc.);

Knowledge - the information that people create about natural and social phenomena; reflection of reality in human thinking.

Skill - experience acquired in a job [6. 22-p].

A skill - the ability to perform a specific activity or action based on a person's previous experiences.

A skill - experience acquired in psychology as a result of mastering a particular profession.

A variety of methodological issues that need to be addressed in the preparation of theoretical knowledge for practical training and the application of theoretical knowledge in teaching practice should be addressed.

Socio-economic relations in our country has changed in the public education system, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 60 of January 28, 2022 on the "Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No 5712 "On approval of the Concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 637 of September 23, 2020 "On Education", State Inspectorate for Quality Control in Education under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan Ministry of Public Education, Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Approval of criteria for certification of educational institutions" Resolution No. 16 of December 16, 2019, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 22 of February 3, 2022 on additional measures to reform the public education system, Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 8, 2018 No 997 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system", Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No 4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 6108 of November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan". As mentioned, every primary school teacher is faced with the important task of bringing a new approach to education, meeting the methodological, scientific, innovative and modern

requirements. These goals allow to distinguish the specific links for primary education, which are used in the introduction of education in various curricula, textbooks, as well as in the methodological system.

When we say the methodological training of an elementary school teacher, we mean the preparation of him in an integral connection with the general psychological and pedagogical training on the basis of a scientific worldview. The task of such preparation is to acquire certain knowledge and skills in the field of primary education and to educate children through education.

Methodological training is an integral part of the training of primary school teachers and cannot be considered in isolation from their educational activities.

It is especially important for a future primary school teacher to know and take into account the level and capacity of students' mental activities, as it is in these primary grades that the foundation for children's mental development is laid. For future practical activities, private, practical, students are acquired as a result of independent work, in particular, through work done in the teaching of elementary school subjects in seminars, practical and laboratory work.

The purpose of methodical training is to form a creative and modern personality of a future primary school teacher who is able to carry out personal and methodological development in primary school students in the process of teaching primary school subjects.

The system of improving methodological training - innovative pedagogical and information based on the requirements of the national program based on personal and professional characteristics, as well as general cultural (aesthetic, philosophical, didactic, educational), scientific (theoretical, methodological), psychological-pedagogical and competency approach - A complex dynamic system that combines knowledge, skills and competencies in the methods of practical application of communication technologies.

Improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers today depends on the following conditions: socio-personal, general, professional, organizational, methodological, technical, pedagogical and psychological activities.

(Figure 1).

Figure 1. Conditions for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers through distance learning.

Based on the diversified activities of the future primary school teacher in the process of teaching primary school subjects and a competent approach, the following criteria for improving the methodological training of future primary school teachers were identified: Organizational-stimulating , process, integrative, cognitive.

Figure 2. Criteria for improving the modern training of future primary school teachers.

Organizational-motivational - the presence of a signal and desire for development in the future primary school teacher, the existing environment, the presence of motivation for purpose and development, the desire to act and achieve a satisfactory result.

Process-communicative skills - the ability to organize pedagogical communication with students in the educational process, the ability to establish pedagogical relationships with primary school students, parents, colleagues, primary school ability to analyze the level of comprehensibility of the expression of tasks in different teaching programs for students, the ability to simply re-express the task if the student finds it difficult to perform the given task, the ability to create a creative research environment, predict the reaction of primary school students, ability to establish an emotional relationship;

Integrative-personal criteria: integrative-personal-ability to integrate and incorporate primary school sciences with other disciplines, creative potential, the formation of the characteristics of the pursuit of professional growth.

Cognitive-psychological – should know pedagogical knowledge of students-knowledge of young and individual, psychophysiological characteristics of primary school students, forms, methods and tools of organization of the educational process, basic methods of diagnosing students through didactic, remote experiments, innovative pedagogical technologies.

We believe that the application of these conditions and criteria to the educational process will serve to improve the competence of the future primary school teacher in teaching primary school subjects.

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